

ASSESSMENT ON THE CRITERION OF SELECTING QUALIFIED APPLICANTS IN HOTEL AND TOURISM INDUSTRY AMONGST GRADUATES OF SELECTED SUC'S AND HEI'S: BASIS FOR EMPLOYABILITY

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to explore, gauge and identify the criterion of selecting qualified applicants in Hotel and Tourism Industry amongst graduates from selected SUC's and HEI'S: Basis for Employability. The data are collected from different hotel and tourism companies who are also considered partners of some SUC'S and HEI's on On-the- Job Training where students are deployed to undergo trainings in different areas of hotel and tourism sector specifically asked 10 (ten) Five Star Hotels, 10 (ten) Travel Agencies, 10 (ten) Restaurants, 5 (five) Airline and Aviation company and 5 (five) from Resort Operations as the respondents of this study. The study used descriptive survey research design and data collection was administered through Google Forms. Initially, participants were also invited to a Focus Group Discussion where their inputs were asked regarding their opinions about the resumption of face-to-face on-the-job training. Since they are already attended the Focus Group Discussion, they were also invited to answer the survey questionnaire related to this study. Questionnaire and documentary analysis were the data gathering tools employed in the study. There is a significant factors and criterions in selecting qualified applicants in Hotel and Tourism Industry as basis for employability. The challenges met by the researcher was respondents has different set of criterions in selecting qualified applicants thus, study may also recommend and suggest standardized or uniform criterion in selecting qualified applicants in hotel and tourism industry.

Keywords: *Criterion for Selection, Specific Qualifications, Employability, Specific Skills needed, Work- Integrated Learning*

INTRODUCTION

What kinds of credentials are preferred by companies in the hospitality and tourist industries? There are a few positions within the hospitality industry that simply need a high school certificate. Getting a degree is your best bet if you want to work in a more senior capacity and increase your annual income as a result. These days, a bachelor's degree is the minimum educational requirement for most jobs and is in great demand. In most cases, the selection criteria for a post will be broken down into the following four categories: Education and other formal credentials, job-specific skills and knowledge, non-job-specific skills, and knowledge, as well as personal qualities and traits, are the standard that is considered by all employers in the hospitality and tourist industry when choosing competent candidates. Some of these are as follows: customer service skills, networking skills, communication skills, flexibility skills, organizational skills, language skills, commitment, can-do attitude, multi-tasking skills, and cultural awareness.

The main credentials, training, abilities, knowledge, personal traits, skills, and experience that a person must have in order to do a job successfully are what are referred to as the selection criteria. To be eligible for consideration as a possible employee in the hotel and tourist business, applicants need to demonstrate that they satisfy the selection criteria. Employers in the hotel and tourist industries look for candidates that are skilled in active listening, creating rapport, problem resolution, and organizing. Education levels ranging from those requiring less than a high school diploma to those requiring a college degree are often required for careers in the tourist and hospitality industries. The employee selection, staffing models, and employee development objectives of an organization are all supported by the business's ability to define acceptable criteria for its recruiting and selection procedures. Criteria include having sufficient and competent workers, being committed to having fair employment practices, having workplace norms, and having pre-employment requirements such as experiences, potentials, hard and soft talents, and cultural compatibility. COVID-19 has had a disproportionate impact on education and employment and livelihood options. Particularly on the internship program of students taking hospitality and tourism courses. Their readiness and skills are huge important for them to land a job. On a brighter side, a lot of students graduated with Latin Honor or flying colors but there is no assurance on the quality of their performance.

When recruiting a candidate, skills and experience are both very significant factors to consider. Candidates, however, should also have a solid cultural and personal fit with both you and your firm. This will guarantee that they are pleased, which will in turn drive them to perform to the best of their abilities. Look for applicants who are responsible, have a strong interest in the position they are applying for, and who share the values of the organization. Higher education institutions are focusing their attention on concerns of employability and productivity as key to their strategic orientation. This fascination is linked to many human capital theories of innovation and economic success. The expansion of a country's stock of human capital is a precondition for economic expansion. According to Ramirez, Cruz, and Alcantara (2014), the knowledge and capabilities of a country's population are the engine that drives the nation's economy. The needs for talents continue to shift in tandem with changes brought about by globalization, technological advancements, and outside investment. Graduates' employability is one of the factors that determine the efficacy of an academic institution. The character of graduates is largely determined by the quality of instruction and facilities, as these factors help to ensure that graduates are endowed with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to work in their respective disciplines. Mitchell and Ashley (2006) also noted that tourism's most significant positive effect on the impoverished is the creation of local jobs. Tourism is substantially more labor-intensive than other non-agricultural industries, as evidenced by cross-national comparison data.

Work-Integrated Learning, often known as WIL, is widely regarded as an important tactic for increasing graduate employability. In recent years, graduate employability has extended to include a broad range of skills, traits, and other indicators, such as networks, professional-identity, and active citizenship. This shift occurred as a result of a shift in the focus of the field from academics to the workforce. This special issue contains contemporary research on work-integrated learning (WIL) and employability, and it addresses the subject of how WIL helps to enhancing the employability outcomes of students and graduates. The study was undertaken to determined employability of graduates and to identify the factors or criterion on selecting qualified hospitality and tourism applicants soon. Specifically, it sought to determine specific criterions, standards, skills needed, traits and values that hospitality and Tourism Company

are looking for. This study will also identify the importance of WIL or Work Integration Learning in helping students to more prepared and ready to accept the industry standards and norms that each company are looking for.

Lastly, this study also aims to generate data from hospitality and tourism employers regarding their present selection process when hiring an employee.

Graduates Employability in Asia. The roles of both individual characteristics and labor market conditions; that is, the supply and demand side of employability. Hillage and Pollard (1998) developed a broad definition that involves three main elements:

1. The ability to gain initial employment, which creates an interest in how the education system deals with the “key skills,” career advice and an understanding of the world of work.
2. The ability to maintain employment and engage in “transitions” between jobs and roles within the same organization that would allow one to meet new requirements.
3. The ability to obtain new employment.

Role of Higher Education Institutions. Since the nature of the education system has often been pinpointed to be responsible for the graduates’ inability to be readily absorbed into the labor market, the role of the HEIs will be emphasized in this paper. According to de la Harpe et al. (2000), current undergraduate programs do not equip students with the professional and continuous learning skills necessary for professional success. (United Nations, 2005) The higher education system has failed to meet the requirements of the current labor market.

Studies on Employability and Productivity of Graduates. Human capital theory has recently reframed education and training as predominantly economic instruments that are essential for participation in the global economy. Foray and Lundvall (1996) contend that the overall economic performance of Western nations is increasingly correlated with their knowledge assets and learning capabilities.

The graduate employability agenda has been taken up by universities, and their responses have included a reexamination of the characteristics that their graduates should have, as well as a focus on the development of generic abilities in their student bodies, which might make graduates appealing to many employers in a range of job situations and fields of study. This essay investigates the commonly held beliefs on the attributes that should be desired in a graduate, and then challenges those beliefs. It implies that generic skill development is an insufficient approach to the problem of graduate employability and that universities should foster wider career management competence in students for better graduate outcomes in the immediate and long-term. This would enhance graduate outcomes both in the short-term and in the long-term.

Graduate attributes. "The qualities, skills, and understandings a university community agrees its students would desirably develop during their time at the institution and, consequently, shape the contribution they are able to make in their profession and as a citizen," as defined by Bowden et al. (2000). Every Australian college or institution has its own ideal graduate profile. Australian government and business groups have each provided their own sets of recommendations (Australian Chamber of Commerce and Industry, 2002).

Few efforts have been undertaken to find overlaps across lists, synthesize qualities based on research (cf. Barrie, 2004; Nunan, 1999), or point out gaps in existing lists. This is in part because the meanings of the many characteristic categories contained in the lists are interpreted differently by different persons.

Graduate employability. Narrow definitions of employability place more of an emphasis on a person's talents and dispositions that could make them appealing to future employers. These definitions tend to place more of a focus on short-term job results, although this is not always the case. Employer groups have, for reasons that are quite understandable, often adopted definitions of this sort. The Confederation of British Industry (1999) defined employability as "the possession by the individual of the qualities and competencies required to meet the changing needs of employers and customers." Employability skills are described as "skills required not only to gain employment but also to progress within an enterprise so that one can achieve one's potential and successfully contribute to enterprise strategic directions" (Australian Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ACCI) and Business Council of Australia (BCA), 2002). Employability skills are defined by these two organizations as "skills required not only to gain employment but also to progress within an enterprise so that one can achieve one's potential and successfully contribute to enterprise strategic directions." Policy papers from the Australian Government have accepted and supported constrained definitions of employability ever since discussions on graduate employability in Australia first began (for instance, Department of Education, Science & Training, 2004, and Department of Employment, Training & Youth Affairs, 2000). Since the beginning of the debates, these definitions have been present.

Broader Definitions of Employability. Even though Australian higher education continues to be dominated by restricted notions of employability, there are conceptualizations that suggest more comprehensive approaches to employability. These conceptualizations consider different aspects of the labor market and an individual's personality (McQuaid & Lindsay, 2005); disciplinary distinctions (Barrie, 2004, 2006); and the placement of work within the context of the person's life (Rychen & Salganik, 2003).

Career Management Skills. Given the recent shift in the labor market away from job security and toward ongoing changes in tasks and roles, one might anticipate that career management skills, or the aptitudes needed for successfully navigating the workplace and managing the career-building process, would be explicitly included in the employability and that discussions about generic skills policy would take place.

Evidence suggests that colleges still have a lot of room to grow in terms of helping students build their career management skills, but (Watts, 2005). Many university graduates are underprepared to pick among a bewildering array of shifting jobs and training options while pursuing a career, according to studies (Lamb & McKenzie, 2001; OECD, 2002a). Review of Career Guidance Policies in Australia Many students in higher education "appears to have little understanding of why they are there or where it is leading," according to the OECD's 2002a publication Country Note."

Career Management Skills and Employability. It is possible to define career management as the capacity to develop a career; to purposefully manage the interplay between employment, learning, and other parts of an individual's life over the lifetime (Haines, Scott, & Lincoln, 2003; Watts, 1998; Webster, Wooden, & Marks, 2004). Research by Watts (1998) and Haines, Scott, and Lincoln (2003) served as the foundation for this idea. The potential

to contribute more effectively to economic development via better employability, productivity, and educational/work efficiency is a less-publicized benefit of well-developed career management abilities (Gillie & Gillie Isenhour, 2003; Killeen, White, & Watts, 1992; Mayston, 2002). In terms of both individual and social wellness, the advantages of career management have been recognised (Gillie & Gillie Isenhour, 2003; Rychen & Salganik, 2003). a framework that outlines the abilities that are essential for improving graduate employability and how career management is essential to the process.

Employability Skills. Employability skills are the abilities that are immediately applicable to acquiring and sustaining employment (Harvey, 2001; McQuaid & Lindsay, 2005). Employability skills are the skills that are directly relevant to obtaining and maintaining job. They consist of the general and discipline-specific skills necessary for performance in a work setting; and career management skills, which may be broken down into two different types of competence: self-management and career development. Knowledge and skills related to career management are necessary for employability because they play a significant role in deciding whether, to what degree, in what way, when and where general and discipline-specific abilities are taught, shown (for example, in an application for a job), and employed. This makes career management knowledge and skills crucial to employability.

Underpinning Traits and Dispositions. According to Jarvis (2003) and McMahon et al. (2003), underlying qualities and dispositions are the predecessors that underpin the effective development and use of career management abilities. Theorists are divided on whether these foundational traits can be developed during higher education and, if so, whether they should be (Chanock, 2003; Knight & Yorke, 2003a), but there is some evidence linking some of these traits with relatively good graduate employment outcomes and higher levels of career success. Students who have high levels of intrinsic drive and professional self-efficacy are more likely to achieve great outcomes educationally (Evans & Burck, 1992) and have better school-to-work transition experiences (Pinquart, Juang, & Silbereisen, 2003), according to the findings of another research. These findings were published in Evans & Burck (1992). When these people go to their jobs, they seem to be substantially happier with their employment and their performance is significantly higher than that of their coworkers (Judge & Bono, 2001).

Discipline-Specific Skills. These are the competencies that are generally taught as part of university curriculum in order to prepare students to meet certain vocational needs. These abilities are often derived from specialized fields, fields of study, or subject matter regions. For instance, a graduate in biochemistry should have the capacity to relate theoretical concepts to practical situations in biochemistry in order to plan and execute research in the laboratory. An individual who has graduated from a statistics program should be able to analyze and interpret data using suitable statistical methods.

Generic Skills. The talents that have been addressed before in this text as being transferrable are examples of generic skills. These talents are the ones that are most often referred to as 'employability skills' in university, policy, and employer graduate attribute lists, such as the ACCI/BCA Employability talents Framework (ACCI and BCA, 2002). Skills like information literacy, dealing with technology, written and verbal communication, working in teams, and numeracy are included in this category of abilities.

Self-Management Skills. These skills are connected to how a person views and evaluates himself in terms of their values, talents, interests, and ambitions. These competences have a strong connection to the idea of professional identity (Arthur, Inkson, & Pringle, 1999; Jones & Filippi, 1996), which may be defined as the way in which an individual's components of themselves and their work responsibilities are viewed to be congruent with one another. Day and Allen (2004) found that the career identity subscale of the career motivation scale they employed strongly predicted pay levels, subjective reports, or career success and work performance. This was discovered in their investigation into the relationship between mentorship and professional achievement.

Career Building Skills. The abilities necessary to construct a successful career include the ability to locate and use knowledge about careers, labor markets, and the world of work; subsequently, the ability to locate, secure, and keep gainful employment; and finally, the ability to exploit career possibilities in order to improve one's career or achieve other desired results. It has been hypothesized that the development of this form of competence would lead to more realistic expectations of the labor market (Watts, 1999) and less mismatches between the supply and demand of the labor market, which will result in negative employment outcomes (Mayston, 2002; Watts, 1999). Both hypotheses have not yet been proven. Through the process of proactive career management, a student who is aware of a high unemployment rate in a particular occupation or geographical location can draw on their skills in self-management and career-building to construct alternative career scenarios that involve different locations, training options, occupational choices, or work modes.

Career Management Skills Development at University. A broader variety of employability skills than merely generic abilities, including concepts of career and self-management, may be demonstrated to have favorable benefits on graduate learning outcomes and employability, as well as on a more general economic level. This is something that can be regarded as having positive implications on the economy. If institutions of higher education take on a more active role in the process of teaching students how to manage their careers, it is likely that this will have a positive effect on the economy. This argues that universities must begin to engage with the employability agenda in a complete and active manner, including the development of career building and skills in self-management, in order to stay competitive in a broad training market where providers compete for students and funds. Therefore, several concerns and things to think about in relation to the integration of skills for career management within the university experience become obvious.

Management of self/ Self-Management. Self-Management is an alternative to the traditional, hierarchical method of organizing we see most often in modern organizations. There are a few key ideas that are central to the Self-Management philosophy, namely that:

- People are generally happier when they have control over their own life (and work)
- It doesn't make a lot of sense to give the decision-making authority to the person that furthest (literally) away from the actual work being done
- When you give good people more responsibility, they tend to flourish
- The traditional hierarchical model of organizations is not scalable—in fact, it's a recipe for a slow, painful death

- There's an undeniable link between freedom and economic prosperity in nations around the world—and, further, an undeniable link between lack of freedom and corruption at the national level. The same is true of human organizations in general.

Some principles practices of Self-Management are reasonably commonplace—self-directed work teams, employee empowerment, distributed decision making, "flattening" the organization, elimination of bureaucratic red tape. These concepts are widely accepted as desirable goals in our respective organizations, and all of these have flavors of Self-

Management.

But true Self-Management is more than just a set of "flavor of the month" business trends; it's a fundamental mind-shift in the way we view human organizations, management, and organizational strategy. We can talk about freedom in the workplace, and we'll be talking about something that is a part of Self-Management, but we aren't really talking about Self-Management; we can talk about employee empowerment, and we'll be talking about something that's fundamental to Self-Management, but employee empowerment alone doesn't get you Self-Management.

Self-Management, simply stated, is an organizational model wherein the traditional functions of a manager (planning, coordinating, controlling, staffing, and directing) are pushed out to all participants in the organization instead of just to a select few. Each member of the organization is personally responsible for forging their own personal relationships, planning their own work, coordinating their actions with other members, acquiring requisite resources to accomplish their mission, and taking corrective action with respect to other members when needed.

Management of others/ Management Competency. Managing Others Assigning work to others and telling them what to do is not the same as effectively managing them. Managing others requires a set of people skills that, when combined with a strong sense of integrity and professionalism, allows you to work through other people to accomplish objectives. As a manager, you must encourage performance through motivation and feedback and hold people accountable.

As you might guess, it would be impossible to provide a comprehensive primer in just a few pages. Many books have been written on this topic. Here, we try to provide you a general overview of the most important issues:

Demonstrate Strength of Character. Personal strength of character is one of the most important competencies of management. A manager must possess a sense of personal responsibility and accountability. Develop your own personal code of conduct and always adhere to it. Doing so will inspire and motivate others to do their personal best.

Develop and Share Your Expertise. The best managers continually expand their knowledge and grow their skill set so that they increase their contribution to the organization. In turn, they share this knowledge and expertise with peers and subordinates to help them move the business forward.

Take the time to become thoroughly knowledgeable about your organization and the business it is in. Attend briefings and presentations by others in the company. Read information published by your organization, such as an annual report. Stay current by reading your industry's trade journals; maintain a network within and outside your organization to anticipate and be aware of new trends. Stay current with new technologies. If you have an area of technical expertise, read, and take occasional courses to maintain those skills. Share your knowledge and expertise with others in ways that will help everyone achieve their business objectives.

Management of tasks. Task management is the process of managing a task through its life cycle. It involves planning, testing, tracking, and reporting. Task management can help either individual achieve goals or groups of individuals collaborate and share knowledge for the accomplishment of collective goals. Tasks are also differentiated by complexity, from low to high. Effective task management requires managing all aspects of a task, including its status, priority, time, human and financial resources assignments, re-currency, notifications and so on.

These can be lumped together broadly into the basic activities of task management. Managing multiple individuals or team tasks may require specialized software, for example, workflow or project management software. In fact, many people believe that task management should serve as a foundation for project management activities.

Task management may form part of project management and process management and can serve as the foundation for efficient workflow in an organization. Project managers adhering to task-oriented management have a detailed and up-to-date project schedule and are usually good at directing team members and moving the project forward.

Employment Opportunities for Graduates. The researcher gathered information from Philippine Overseas Employment Administration (POEA) to help us know our options or job opportunities waits for us abroad; here are some data or a list of Hospitality Management related jobs: The tourism and hospitality industry is the world's largest industry and offers unrivaled opportunities for an exciting and rewarding career. The Hotel and Restaurant Management program responds to this challenge with a comprehensive blend of practical and theoretical courses driven by industry. The program's performance-based training is increasingly recognized as vital to promoting the standards of excellence required in today's business world. Graduates of Hotel and Restaurant Management will have a broad base of management and technical skills, which enable them to immediately be productive in the workplace.

It is the intent of the Myrtle Beach Area Chamber of Commerce to clarify the definitions of employment classification and status so that employees understand their own classification, status, and benefits eligibility. The following does not guarantee employment for any specified period. Accordingly, the definitions below do not change the fact that all Chamber employees are employees-at-will. The right to terminate the employment relationship at will at any time is retained by both the employee and the Chamber.

Qualitative insights from the employer's perception about graduate's skills attribute that is valued by the employers.

The scoping interviews with employers and HEI organizations found that there are characteristics, skills and knowledge and intellectual capability elements that are required for specific roles. In addition, combinations of transferable skills were also deemed particularly relevant. These were:

- Team working
- Problem solving
- Self-management
- Knowledge of the business
- Literacy and numeracy relevant to the post
- ICT knowledge
- Good interpersonal and communication skills
- Ability to use own initiative but also to follow instructions

- Leadership skills where necessary.

In addition to these skills, employers also highlighted the need for attitudes and outlooks, including motivation, tenacity, and commitment. Overall, this is in line with the UKCES (2009a) findings. A further similarity with the UKCES report was that employers and their representative organizations thought that specific definitions of employability were less important than an agreed focus on how to promote employability skills and attributes. Work experience, internships, and extra-curricular activities while at university was seen by employers and graduates as particularly helpful in developing these transferable skills. Some of the employers and almost all graduates involved first degrees from full-time courses in 2006/2007 were employed or in further study within six months of completing their degrees and attributed this to their Advancing Skills for Professionals in the Rural Economy (ASPIRE) programme. Clearly, there is more to employability than securing a job, such as making a productive contribution to the organizations, economy, and society, but these examples provide indications of the value added by their courses and initiatives. While relatively few, research studies conducted on the longer-term value and impact of HEI employability measures indicate that work placements can be particularly effective. Hall et al. (2009) report that Overall, it appears that the placement year is equipping students well with opportunities for self-development and personal effectiveness in a dynamic teamwork environment and that these qualities are key to employability.

Objectives

The main concern of the study is to assess and identify the criterion used by the hospitality and tourism industry on selecting qualified applicants amongst selected SUC's and HEI's:

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the criterion used by the following hospitality and tourism sector;
 - 1.1. Five Star Hotels
 - 1.2. Travel Agencies
 - 1.3. Restaurant
 - 1.4. Airline and Aviation company
 - 1.5. Resort
2. What are the existing soft skills and hard skills does students possess in terms of the following?
 - 2.1. Problem Solving Skills
 - 2.2. Communication Skills
 - 2.3. Adaptability Skills
 - 2.4. Critical Thinking Skills
 - 2.5. Time Management Skills
 - 2.6. Inter-Personal Skills
 - 2.7. Level of Skills with the use of Modern Business Tools and Technology
 - 2.8. Data Analytics

2.9. Marketing and Graphic Design

3. How does the level of training and experiences describe and measure in terms of the following dimensions?
 - 3.1. Job Performances from the perspective of the Employers?
 - 3.2. Job Performances from the perspective of the graduates?
4. What is the phenomenon of employability of the HRM and Tourism students in terms of:
 - 4.1. Employment Data Status
 - 4.2. Waiting Time for Employment
 - 4.3. Number of Times Applied for a Job
 - 4.4. Nature of Employment
5. What were the issues and problems encountered by the graduates/applicants?
6. What curriculum enhancement be proposed to further improve the program to match the employability skills and meet the standards/ criterion of hotel and tourism companies when hiring an applicant?

METHODS

Research Design

The study used descriptive survey research design and data collection was administered through Google Forms. Initially, participants were also invited to a Focus Group Discussion where their inputs were asked regarding their opinions about the resumption of face-to-face on-the-job training. Since they are already attended the Focus Group Discussion, they were also invited to answer the survey questionnaire related to this study. Questionnaire and documentary analysis were the data gathering tools employed in the study.

Population and Sampling

The data are collected from different hotel and tourism companies who are also considered partners of some SUC'S and HEI's on On-the- Job Training where students are deployed to undergo trainings in different areas of hotel and tourism sector specifically asked 10 (ten) Five Star Hotels, 10 (ten) Travel Agencies, 10 (ten) Restaurants, 5 (five) Airline and Aviation company and 5 (five) from Resort Operations as the respondents of this study.

Instrumentation

The researcher did an academic reading to come up with relevant information regarding how the research questionnaires were developed. By familiarizing what is already known about the topic, the researcher endeavored to construct the research instrument guided by related literature and studies and in consultation with experts in the field of hoteliers. With assistance from the experts, the researcher came up with the tool that yielded answers to the

statement of the problem. The tool was a structured survey questionnaire where the respondents indicated a (√) mark on the corresponding numerical equivalent of each descriptor. In rating the descriptive statements that indicated the extent from 5 as the highest with a corresponding verbal interpretation of highly productive down to 1 as the lowest or not productive.

The research instrument was constructed in a way that the language used was void of technical terms for easy understanding of the respondents. A pilot study was conducted by the researcher at the Our Lady of Fatima University of Batch 2021, which was not included in the study, involving ten (10) HRM students. A pilot study is a preliminary small-scale study that the researcher was conducted in order to help to decide how best to conduct larger-scale research. Using a pilot study, the researcher identified or refined the research questions, figure out what methods are best for pursuing them, and estimate how much time and resources were necessary to complete the larger version and wider scope, among other things. In addition, it is useful in troubleshooting unforeseen issues in the study and determining whether research is feasible.

Data Collection

The data were gathered, collated, tabulated, and subjected for statistical treatment. In addition, the researcher used a survey questionnaire as a method of data collection. The researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to the chosen industry partners where we usually deploy our students for On-The-Job-Training as a subject of the study through online platform like Google Forms. Also, the researcher used their social media account to gather the respondent to the study.

Data Analysis

The Descriptive Statistics involving the use of weighted mean and ranking were applied to know the level of Job Performance of the applicant’s knowledge and skills regarding their chosen courses.

Data Processing and Statistical Treatment

The data gathered were processed using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The following statistical tools were utilized in data analysis:

1. The phenomenon of employability of the applicants was analyzed using frequency counts, percentage procedure, mean, and standard deviation.
2. The importance of skills of the applicants was examined using a Five-Point Likert Scale interpreted as follows:

Rating Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50-5.0	Very Important
4	3.50-4.49	Moderately Important
3	2.50-3.49	Neutral
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Important

1	1.0-1.49	Not Important
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3. The level of training and experienced of the applicants was measured through applicants’ perceptions of the relevance of their program to the requirements of the industry were analyzed using a five-point Likert Scale interpreted as follows.

Rating Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50-5.0	Very Relevant
4	3.50-4.49	Relevant
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Relevant
2	1.50-2.49	Irrelevant
1	1.0-1.49	Very Irrelevant

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table I. Criterion used by the hospitality and tourism company in respective sectors are as follows:

Criteria	Frequency	Percentage	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
Five Star Hotels (10)				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education & Other Formal Credentials 	10	100%	1.5	Very Important
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job Specific Skills & Knowledge 	8	80%	3	Very Important
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-Job Specific Skills & Knowledge 	7	70%	4	Moderately Important
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Attributes and Traits 	10	100%	1.5	Very Important
Travel Agency (10)				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education & Other Formal Credentials 	10	100%	1	Very Important

• Job Specific Skills & Knowledge	9	90%	2.5	Very Important
• Non-Job Specific Skills & Knowledge	8	70%	4	Very Important
• Personal Attributes and Traits	9	90%	2.5	Very Important
Restaurant (10)				
• Education & Other Formal Credentials	10	100%	1	Very Important
• Job Specific Skills & Knowledge	9	90%	2.5	Very Important
• Non-Job Specific Skills & Knowledge	8	70%	4	Very Important
• Personal Attributes and Traits	9	90%	2.5	Very Important
Airline & Aviation (5)				
• Education & Other Formal Credentials	5	100%	1.75	Very Important
• Job Specific Skills & Knowledge	5	100%	1.75	Very Important
• Non-Job Specific Skills & Knowledge	4	80%	4	Very Important
• Personal Attributes and Traits	5	100%	1.75	Very Important

Resort (5)

• Education & Other Formal Credentials	5	100%	1.75	Very Important
• Job Specific Skills & Knowledge	5	100%	1.75	Very Important
• Non-Job Specific Skills & Knowledge	4	80%	4	Very Important
• Personal Attributes and Traits	5	100%	1.75	Very Important

Table I, shows that the hospitality and tourism company are almost the same preference in selecting qualified applicants. The result shows that education and other formal trainings are very important since most the company answered the same and it all ranked number one. On the other hand, Job Specifics Skills and Knowledge is equally important as it also got a very important result same as personal traits and attributes. Non-Job specifics got moderately important result particularly in Five Star hotel category.

Table II. Important Skills of the Applicants

Soft Skills, Hard Skills	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Problem Solving Skills	32	80%	9
Communication Skills	38	95%	2.5
Adaptability Skills	40	100%	1
Critical Thinking Skills	37	93%	3.75
Time Management Skills	37	93%	3.75
Inter-Personal Skills	38	95%	2.5
Level of Skills with the use of Modern Business Tools and Technology	37	93%	3.75
Data Analytics	35	88%	7
Marketing and Graphic Design	34	85%	8

Table II revealed that adaptability skills is very important having 100% and ranked one in the result. Communication Skills, and Inter-Personal Skills are also very important in establishing good relationship and teamwork with the team having 95% as the result. Critical Thinking, Time Management Skills, and Level of Skills in using Modern Business Tools and Technology are also very important in today's trends of modern technology. On the other hand, Data Analytics, Marketing and Graphic Design and Problem Solving is something to be develop and enhance.

Table III. Work Attitude. The results were tallied and were interpreted to measure the Job Performance of OLFU graduates in their perspective. Among 10 qualities of Work Attitudes, results are as follows: having the highest result of 4.80, highly productive graduates and employers believe that they all have social manners and right conduct while they are in the hotel industry having their training. Trainees and even the managers and supervisors observe proper hygiene and grooming to become highly productive, giving it 4.65 as the over-all mean. Trainees believe among themselves that they are committed to their work assignment as well as the employers (4.61), making it also as highly productive. Other highly productive results are as follows for work attitude; trainee has a sense of initiative (4.50), trainee shows interest to work giving it (4.55), the trainee is also reliable and responsible as a result shows giving it (4.50), and trainee observes honesty at work having (4.50) as the over-mean.

Mean score and descriptive equivalent on the training and experience of the applicants in terms of work attitude

Criteria/ Indicators	Applicants Self- Assessment		Employers/Supervisors Assessment		Over-All Assessment	
	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Applicant can easily adapt to work conditions.	4.23	Productive	4.26	Productive	4.25	Productive
2. Applicant has a commitment to work	4.62	Highly Productive	4.60	Highly Productive	4.61	Highly Productive
3. Applicant has cooperation with the needs of the establishment.	4.40	Productive	4.55	Highly Productive	4.48	Productive
4. Applicant has a sense of initiative	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive
5. Applicant observes punctuality	4.40	Productive	4.30	Productive	4.35	Productive
6. Applicant shows interest in work	4.45	Productive	4.65	Highly Productive	4.55	Highly Productive
7. Applicant is reliable and responsible	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive
8. Applicant has social manners and right conduct	4.70	Highly Productive	4.90	Highly Productive	4.80	Highly Productive

9. Applicant has proper hygiene and grooming	4.65	Highly Productive	4.65	Highly Productive	4.65	Highly Productive
10. Applicant observes honesty at work	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive
Average Mean	4.50	Highly Productive	4.54	Highly Productive	4.52	Highly Productive

**Highly productive – 5.0-4.50, Productive- 4.49-3.5, Moderately productive 3.49-2.50 Limited on productivity 2.49-1.50, Not Productive- 1.49.1.0*

However, this might be an eye-opener to Our Lady of Fatima University that three (3) indicators that have productive over-all mean can be considered as the room for improvement. A trainee should be given institutional assessment prior to the job training to further prepare them on the work conditions of the industry, having a 4.25 over-all mean given by both graduates and employers. Punctuality is always an issue among everyone else; therefore, OLFU should give emphasis on student’s punctuality prior to the job training having 4.35 as the overall mean given by both trainees and employers. Lastly, teach and train students on cooperation and teamwork. Having 4.48 over-all means to make them realize that the success of the team is team effort and cooperation.

Table IV. Functional Effectiveness. The results were tallied and interpreted to measure the Job Performance of OLFU graduates in their perspective. Among the seven indicators of functional effectiveness, results are as follows: having the highest over-all mean given by both graduates and employers of (4.77) considered highly productive falls under the achieving establishment’s standards and procedures. Also, having the same descriptive equivalent of highly productive given by both graduates and employers (4.50) for a sense of urgency and accuracy to work, resourcefulness to work, and contributes to a positive work environment. However, most of the companies find the effectiveness of manpower if they are systematic and organized; thus, being the lowest over-all mean given by both graduates and managers of (4.27) for both organized and systematic and trainee must be goal-oriented and result-oriented. Lastly, the trainee should be trained to become dependable since the result shows (4.35); even this one is considered productive, it can still be improved.

Mean score and descriptive equivalent on the training and experience acquired by the applicants in terms of Functional Effectiveness

Criteria/ Indicators	Graduates Self- Assessment		Employers/Supervisors Assessment		Over-All Assessment	
	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.Applicant has a sense of urgency and accuracy to work	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive
2.Applicant is resourceful to work	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive
3.Applicant is dependable	4.40	Productive	4.30	Productive	4.35	Productive

4. Applicant achieves the establishment's standards and procedure	4.68	Highly Productive	4.86	Highly Productive	4.77	Highly Productive
5. Applicant is organized and systematic	4.25	Productive	4.28	Productive	4.27	Productive
6. Applicant contributes a positive work environment	4.52	Highly Productive	4.50	Highly Productive	4.51	Highly Productive
7. Applicant is goal-oriented and result-oriented	4.25	Productive	4.28	Productive	4.27	Productive
Average Mean	4.44	Productive	4.46	Productive	4.45	Productive

**Highly productive – 5.0-4.50, Productive- 4.49-3.5, Moderately productive 3.49-2.50 Limited on productivity 2.49-1.50, Not Productive- 1.49.1.0*

Perceived Relevance of Hotel and Restaurant Management Curriculum Program and Tourism Program of Our Lady of Fatima University

Table V.

Mean score and descriptive equivalent on the relevance of hotel and restaurant management and Tourism Management curriculum program of Our Lady of Fatima University

Criteria/ Indicators	Graduates Self- Assessment		Employers/Supervisors Assessment		Over-All Assessment	
	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Communication Skills	4.60	Very Relevant	4.50	Very Relevant	4.55	Very Relevant
Human Relation Skills	4.55	Very Relevant	4.80	Very Relevant	4.68	Very Relevant
Entrepreneurial Skills	4.40	Relevant	4.35	Relevant	4.38	Relevant
Problem-Solving Skills	4.25	Relevant	4.30	Relevant	4.28	Relevant
Critical Thinking Skills	4.45	Relevant	4.50	Very Relevant	4.48	Relevant
National Certification (TESDA)	4.80	Very Relevant	4.60	Very Relevant	4.70	Very Relevant
International Certification (AHA)	4.60	Very Relevant	4.50	Very Relevant	4.55	Very Relevant
Grand Mean	4.52	Very Relevant	4.51	Very Relevant	4.52	Very Relevant

Issues and Problems Encountered by the applicants

The issues and problems encountered by the graduates were identified in three categories: work-life balance issues, contractualization issues, and turn- over rate issues.

Work-life balance issue. In terms of work-life balance issues, more than half of the graduates, or 52.49 percent, identified job matching as a problem. A total of 66 respondents, or 36.46 percent, disclosed that complying with job requirements is a problem. The rest cannot easily adjust to the work environment (8.29%) and preparedness for the industry set up (2.76%).

Table VIA

Mean score and descriptive equivalent on issues and problems encountered by the applicants in terms of work-life balance issues/problems

Categories	Frequency	%
1. The employee cannot easily adjust and adapt to the work environment	15	8.29%
2. Job Matching	95	52.49%
3. Preparedness for the industry set-up	5	2.76%
4. Complying with Job Requirements	66	36.46%
Total	181	100.00%

Contractualization issue. Other problems cited were about Contractualization. A total of 105 respondents, or the highest result 58.01percent, cited the company practice of hiring workers as “contractual” rather than as regular. Next is the non-giving of employee benefits, which got 28.18%. Lastly, the establishment offers standardized salary/compensation was considered a problem by 13.81% of the total respondents.

Table VIB

Contractualization Issues/Problems

Categories	Frequency	%
1. Company practice of hiring workers as “contractual” rather than as regular	105	58.01%
2. Non-giving of Employee Benefits	51	28.18%
3. The establishment offers a standardized salary/compensation	25	13.81%
Total	181	100.00%

Table 6C presents the Turn-over Rates and Issues and problems. Having the highest percentage was employees are often hired as temporary or seasonal workers having 77.34%, followed by high employee turnover-over of workers with 16.02%. Next is, Frequent employees prepare to work during summer or part-time jobs having 5.52%, and lastly, Low wages tend to alienate workers, who may leave soon as they get a better offer having 1.10% as the lowest.

Table VIC

Turn-Over Rate Issues/Problems

Categories	Frequency	%
1. Employees are often hired as temporary or seasonal workers	140	77.34%
2. Frequent employees prepare to work during summer or part-time jobs	10	5.52%
3. Low wages tend to alienate workers, who	2	1.10%

may leave soon as they get a better offer		
4. turnover-over of employees	29	16.02%
Total	181	100.00%

The issues and problems result from Table 6 A Work-Life Balance Issues, 6 B Contractualization Issue and 6 C Turn-Over Rate Issue are presented and identified to serve as a basis in proposing curricular enhancement for the Hotel and Restaurant Management program and Tourism Program of selected SUC's and HEI's. Our Lady of Fatima University had started to build up and established Academe- Industry Linkages Pathways (AILP) since 2015. From then, they were able to recognize Advisory board members from different hospitality industry fields. The agenda and activities involve syllabi review and co-authorship, review, and validation of the curriculum, and lastly, the introduction of new courses with specializations. Taking –off from the survey of competencies conducted during the first AILP Board Meeting, the Ad Board reviewed the current syllabi of courses offered by both Hospitality and Tourism Management Departments. This aims to develop and strengthen the courses being offered by the university and align them with industry specifications. Most of the Ad Board members reacted positively to the said undertaking, as this will also lead to better-equipped and competent hospitality and tourism professionals in the workforce. Table 14 identifies the highest two problems encountered by the graduates, and the opposite side of the table is the proposed curriculum enhancement made by Our Lady of Fatima University to meet the industry requirements, specifically the skills and competency which the establishment looks forward from the graduates.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Applicants must acquire the necessary knowledge and skills needed to meet the standards of industries, and therefore highly employable.
2. The graduates were found highly productive from the lens of both the graduates themselves and their employers. They are well-rated in terms of work attitude, functional effectiveness, and interpersonal skills in using applied business tools and techniques.
3. Applicants was perceived as very relevant in terms of contemporary requirements, specifically communication skills, human relation skills, entrepreneurial skills, problem-solving skills, and critical thinking skills. The graduates were found compliant with the standards of the TESDA National Certification and the International Certification (AHA).
4. Job matching and complying with job requirements were the top work balance issues encountered by the graduates. The Contractualization issue was a big problem for the graduates. Among the four turn-over rate issues, hiring employees as temporary or seasonal workers was on top of the list.
5. The issues and problems, when viewed with a positive note, could provide significant insights for curriculum improvement. Among those cited were introducing a curriculum with the specialist track, mandatory requirements for completing six TVET Certifications, and further enhancing the academe-industry linkage of all SUC's and HEI's.

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